

An Approach from the Plithogenic DEA to the Calculation of the Efficiency of a Pedagogical Strategy on Basic Digital Competencies in Students of the Basic Education Program at the Bolivarian University of Ecuador

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Abstract. In the context of higher education, the evolution towards a full integration of digital technologies has been significant globally, but its effective implementation varies between different regions and institutions. In Latin America, the adoption of information and communication technologies (ICTs) has been uneven, despite efforts to incorporate digital tools into education. Significant gaps in infrastructure and teacher training persist, which limit educational quality and the full development of digital skills in students. This paper aims to measure the impact of implementing a pedagogical strategy on developing basic digital skills and how it improves the pedagogical skills and innovation capacity of students in the Basic Education career at the Bolivarian University of Ecuador. To achieve this goal, a group of students who receive a program benefiting from this strategy are evaluated. Plithogenic Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) is used for data representation and processing. On the one hand, plithogeny is used to deal with data of different natures; it is a multivariate theory. DEA is a theory based on linear programming that measures the efficiency between input and output variables for multi-criteria decision problems. The combination of both tools allows the research objective to be met.

Keywords: Higher education, digital competence, strategy pedagogical, Plithogeny, plithogenic set, plithogenic neutrosophic set, Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA), plithogenic DEA.

1 Introduction

The digital transformation has reshaped social, economic, and educational dynamics worldwide, making mastery of digital skills an essential requirement for active and productive participation in the 21st century. In higher education, this evolution has generated new demands on students and faculty, who must adapt to learning environments that integrate emerging technologies, innovative methodologies, and constantly updated digital resources. However, this integration process has not been uniform, especially in regions like Latin America, where significant gaps in infrastructure, training, and technological access persist.

In Latin America, and particularly in Ecuador, the integration of digital skills in higher education represents a transcendental challenge for the academic and professional development of university students. Although students possess basic knowledge of digital tools, there are significant deficiencies in advanced skills, such as content creation and security in digital environments. These shortcomings are evident in recent studies, which show an intermediate command of digital skills among students at Ecuadorian higher education institutions, with notable limitations in information management and communication on digital platforms.

The Bolivarian University of Ecuador emphasizes the need to strengthen basic digital skills among students of Basic Education, as this has become an urgent challenge. Although young university students are familiar with everyday technological tools, there is a clear gap between these initial skills and the digital competencies necessary for their professional development as 21st-century educators. This

gap compromises their capacity for pedagogical innovation, limits their critical and creative use of technology, and ultimately affects the quality of the educational process they must lead.

At a broad level, the magnitude of the problem is reflected in the frequency and distribution of digital skills gaps, affecting not only urban areas but also less accessible regions where access to advanced technology is still limited. Research indicates that these challenges are especially significant for vulnerable groups, including low-income students and women, who often face additional barriers to accessing technology education.

The likely causes of this situation include insufficient technological infrastructure at many universities, teacher training that is not always up to date with technological innovations, and a lack of coherent educational policies that prioritize the integration of digital skills into the curriculum. Furthermore, there is limited consensus on the best approaches and practices for teaching and learning these skills, resulting in disparities in the quality of digital education across institutions.

In this context, there is an urgent need to rethink the pedagogical strategies used to train future teachers. It is essential to design and implement methodological proposals that not only promote the instrumental use of technology but also foster critical reflection, the creation of digital content, collaboration in virtual environments, and digital ethics. Training professionals with these capabilities implies going a step further than simply acquiring technical skills; it requires a profound transformation in the way we understand the teaching-learning process, where technology becomes a means to enrich pedagogical thinking and not an end.

The objective of this article is to analyze, design, and validate a pedagogical strategy focused on the development of basic digital competencies to strengthen the pedagogical skills and innovative capacity of students in the Basic Education program at the Bolivarian University of Ecuador. By addressing this problem from a broad perspective, the aim is to provide not only a well-founded diagnosis but also a viable proposal that can be replicated in other institutions in the country. The goal is clear: to contribute to a more equitable, inclusive education adapted to the challenges of the present, in which teachers not only teach with technology but also educate for critical, active, and engaged digital citizenship.

One of the challenges of the study we wish to conduct lies in the diversity of variables that form part of the problem, including those of pedagogical, technological, social, and political origin, among others. Furthermore, there may be uncertainty and indeterminacy in any opinion given, because we are dealing with subjective ideas. To comply with multi-dimensionality, the diversity of the types of variables, uncertainty, and indeterminacy, we use plithogenic neutrosophic sets [1]. Plithogeny theory was introduced by F. Smarandache to model multivariate problems [2]. This theory aims to capture the dynamics between different elements, their opposites, and their neutrals, where neutral also refers to the paradoxical, the contradictory, the inconsistent, the erroneous, and so on [3-5].

Specifically, we will study the impact of the chosen strategy by evaluating a group of students' improvement in certain aspects. To do this, we will combine plithogenic sets with the Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) method [6, 7]. DEA is a mathematical technique used to evaluate the efficiency of productive units, such as companies, hospitals, or educational institutions [8]. It is based on the comparison of multiple inputs (resources used) and outputs (results obtained) to determine how efficient a unit is relative to similar units.

The key concepts of DEA are [9]:

- Relative efficiency: It is not compared with an absolute standard, but with the best performance within the group analyzed.
- Non-parametric model: It does not require a specific functional form for the relationship between inputs and outputs.
- Use in multiple sectors: Applied in economics, health, education, and energy, among others [10-13].

The advantages of the DEA are:

- It allows us to identify best practices within a group,

- It does not require assumptions about the distribution of the data,
- It can handle multiple inputs and outputs simultaneously.

There are several models of DEAs; among the most common are [14]:

- CCR (Charnes, Cooper, and Rhodes) model: Assumes constant returns to scale (CRS), which means that any linear combination of the observed decision units is valid.
- BCC model (Banker, Charnes, and Cooper): Considers variable returns to scale (VRS), allowing convex linear combinations.
- Input- or output-oriented models: Depending on the approach, they may seek to minimize resource use (input) or maximize production (output).

Hybridizing the DEA method with plithogenic neutrosophic sets allows measuring efficiency in more complex data, where the indeterminacy and uncertainty inherent in the variables obtained by subjective measurements are taken into account [6].

This paper is divided into a Materials and Methods section summarizing the main concepts related to DEA and plithogenic sets. The Results section contains the results of the study. The article also has a Conclusion section.

2 Materials and Methods

In this section, we present the theories used to perform the analysis. These are the Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) method and the Plithogenic Sets.

2.1 Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA)

This is a non-parametric method used to calculate the relative efficiency of decision-making units (DMUs) concerning several variables, some inputs, and other outputs [6, 14]. The model is based on linear programming. There are two DEA models; the first is known as CCR and gives a total efficiency score. The second is BCC, which calculates technical efficiency scores for each DMU. Both CCR and BCC models can be configured as input-oriented or output-oriented. The input-oriented CCR model consists of the following problem:

$$\begin{aligned} \max \theta &= \sum_{r=1}^s u_r y_{r0} \\ \text{s.t.} & \\ &\begin{cases} \sum_{i=1}^m v_i x_{i0} = 1 \\ \sum_{r=1}^s u_r y_{rj} - \sum_{i=1}^m v_i x_{ij} \leq 0; j = 1, 2, \dots, n \\ u_r, v_i \geq 0; r = 1, 2, \dots, s; i = 1, 2, \dots, m \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

In this model, there are n DMUs to be evaluated: θ is the efficiency score of the k th DMU; y_{rk} is the r th output of the j th DMU; x_{ij} is the i th input based on the j th DMU; u_r is the weight of the r th output; v_i is the weight of the i th input; m is the number of inputs; s is the number of outputs. This is a linear programming problem.

The output-oriented CCR model consists of the following equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \min \varphi &= \sum_{i=1}^m v_i x_{ij} \\ \text{s.t.} & \\ &\begin{cases} \sum_{r=1}^s u_r y_{r0} = 1 \\ \sum_{r=1}^s u_r y_{rj} - \sum_{i=1}^m v_i x_{ij} \leq 0; j = 1, 2, \dots, n \\ u_r, v_i \geq 0; r = 1, 2, \dots, s; i = 1, 2, \dots, m \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

2.2 Plithogenic Sets

Plithogenic sets generalize neutrosophic sets [1, 15-19]. Moreover, unlike previous sets such as fuzzy

sets, intuitionistic fuzzy sets, and all others, this one takes multidimensionality into account. The idea behind plithogenic sets is to capture the dynamics that exist between different concepts, their opposites, and their neutrals.

A *plithogenic set*, which is denoted by P on a universe of discourse U , is defined by a quintuple (P, a, V, d, c) where:

1. P is a non-empty subset of U , which is the *plithogenic set*.
2. $A = \{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_m\}$, $m \geq 1$ is a set of *one-dimensional attributes*,
3. For each $\alpha \in A$, there is a spectrum of all possible values (or states) S , which can be finite, countably infinite, or continuous infinite, represented by an open, closed, or half-open interval of real numbers or another more general domain.

So, $V \subset S$, $V \neq \emptyset$ is the range of all state values defined by experts as necessary to model the problem being studied. Thus, $V = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$, and $n \geq 1$.

4. d is called the *degree of approval*, defined as indicated in Equation 3:

$$\forall x \in P, d: P \times V \rightarrow \mathcal{P}([0, 1]^z) \quad (3)$$

Therefore, $d(x, v)$ is defined for each pair of elements, one of P and one in V , into the power set of $[0, 1]^z$.

The value of z defines the type of appurtenance; $z = 1$ is a *fuzzy degree of appurtenance*, $z = 2$ corresponds to an *intuitionistic fuzzy degree of appurtenance*, and $z = 3$ characterizes the *neutrosophic degree of appurtenance*.

Let us denote by d_F the *fuzzy degree of appurtenance*, by d_{IF} the *intuitionistic fuzzy degree of appurtenance*, and by d_N the *neutrosophic degree of appurtenance*.

5. In general, there may be a value called dominant, denoted by v_D , which is the one indicated by experts as the reference or the most important.

The *attribute value contradiction degree function* $c: V \times V \rightarrow [0, 1]$ between two attributes v_1 and v_2 satisfies the following properties:

- $c(v_1, v_1) = 0$,
- $c(v_1, v_2) = c(v_2, v_1)$.

This function measures the dissimilarity that exists between the two attributes. Just like d , this is classified into:

- *Fuzzy attribute value contradiction degree function*, which is denoted by c_F ,
- *Intuitionistic fuzzy attribute value contradiction function* that is a function $c_{IF}: V \times V \rightarrow [0, 1]^2$,
- *Neutrosophic attribute value contradiction degree function* that is defined by $c_N: V \times V \rightarrow [0, 1]^3$.

In general, with the plithogenic sets we can define operations of *plithogenic aggregation operators* (intersection (AND), union (OR), implication (\Rightarrow), equivalence (\Leftrightarrow), inclusion relation (partial order), among others) from the fuzzy t-norms (\wedge_F) and the fuzzy t-conorms (\vee_F). These operations can be obtained by linear or nonlinear combinations of t-norms and t-conorms.

If v_D is the dominant value and v_2 is any value, then the operations that appear in Equations 4 and 5 can be defined between them:

$$[1 - c(v_D, v_2)] \cdot (v_D \wedge_F v_2) + c(v_D, v_2) \cdot (v_D \vee_F v_2) \quad (4),$$

$$[1 - c(v_D, v_2)] \cdot (v_D \vee_F v_2) + c(v_D, v_2) \cdot (v_D \wedge_F v_2) \quad (5).$$

Where $c(v_D, v_2)$ denotes the contradiction between v_D and v_2 .

Additionally, it is especially necessary to consider the *Plithogenic Neutrosophic Intersection*:

$$(a_1, a_2, a_3) \wedge_P (b_1, b_2, b_3) = \left(a_1 \wedge_F b_1, \frac{1}{2}[(a_2 \wedge_F b_2) + (a_2 \vee_F b_2)], a_3 \vee_F b_3 \right) \quad (6),$$

The *Plithogenic Neutrosophic Union* is:

$$(a_1, a_2, a_3) \vee_P (b_1, b_2, b_3) = \left(a_1 \vee_F b_1, \frac{1}{2}[(a_2 \wedge_F b_2) + (a_2 \vee_F b_2)], a_3 \wedge_F b_3 \right) \quad (7).$$

To define the *Plithogenic Neutrosophic Inclusion*, we have:

Due to the degrees of contradiction are $c(a_1, a_2) = c(a_2, a_3) = c(b_1, b_2) = c(b_2, b_3) = 0.5$, then: $a_2 \geq [1 - c(a_1, a_2)]b_2$ or $a_2 \geq (1 - 0.5)b_2$ or $a_2 \geq 0.5b_2$ and $c(a_1, a_3) = c(b_1, b_3) = 1$.

When $a_1 \leq b_1$ the opposite applies for $a_3 \geq b_3$, and then $(a_1, a_2, a_3) \leq_P (b_1, b_2, b_3)$ if and only if $a_1 \leq b_1$ and $a_2 \geq 0.5b_2, a_3 \geq b_3$.

3 Results

The study included 23,300 undergraduate students and faculty members from the Bolivarian University of Ecuador. A non-probability sample of 244 participants was selected. The idea of using the plithogenic neutrosophic sets with DAE is as follows:

Pre-strategy assessments are used as inputs, and post-strategy assessments are used as outputs. This would allow for analyzing the relative effectiveness of the digital skills strategy based on the progress observed, as follows:

1. Define assessment units: Each participant and group is a decision-making unit (DMU). DMUs denote participants, and DMGs denote groups.
2. Inputs (before the strategy): Level of digital competence before the intervention, access to technology, and previous training.
3. Outputs (after the strategy): Digital skills after the intervention, productivity, and adoption of technological tools.
4. Application of the unit: Comparing how initial evaluations (inputs) were transformed into final results (outputs).
5. Results analysis: If efficiency is guaranteed after the strategy is implemented, it means it had a positive impact; if not, certain factors could be adjusted.

One of the important elements is to establish the measurement scale, which is a linguistic scale, as shown in [20]:

Table 1. Proposed neutrosophic linguistic scale. Source: [20].

Linguistic Variable	Plithogenic neutrosophic scale
Very Bad (VB)	(0.10, 0.75, 0.85)
Bad (B)	(0.25, 0.60, 0.80)
Medium Bad (MB)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)
Medium (M)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)
Medium Good (MG)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)
Good (G)	(0.80, 0.10, 0.30)
Very Good (VG)	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)

As shown in [16], we apply the following adapted algorithm:

1. The results of the inputs and outputs are evaluated according to the linguistic scale shown in Table 1. To process the data, we work with their plithogenic neutrosophic numbers scale equivalent.
2. The dominant criterion is established, as well as the neutrosophic attribute value contradiction degree function, which is fixed. To aggregate the results by groups, the operator in Equation 4 is selected.

The t-norm minimum and the t-conorm maximum are used. Aggregation using plithogenic neutrosophic numbers is the one that appears in the plithogenic neutrosophic intersection of Equation 6.

3. Each of the aggregation results becomes a plithogenic neutrosophic number, where $X = (\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ is converted to a crisp value using the following score function equation [21]:

$$S(X) = \frac{(2+\alpha-\beta-\gamma)}{3} \quad (8)$$

These values are then rescaled concerning v_D using Equation 4.

4. The traditional DEA method is applied to the crisp data.

After consulting with experts, it was determined that there are three key strategies to strengthen digital competence in a pedagogical university:

1. Integration of Educational Technologies into Teaching: Train teachers in the use of digital tools such as interactive platforms, virtual simulations, and educational software. Incorporate methodologies such as digital project-based learning and gamification.
2. Promoting Digital Culture and Critical Thinking: Develop training spaces where students and teachers reflect on the impact of technology, online security, and the responsible use of information. Digital literacy programs can help improve the search for reliable sources and the ethical handling of data.
3. Creation of Digital Innovation Labs and Networks: Establish innovation labs with access to artificial intelligence, augmented reality, and data analysis tools applied to education. Additionally, foster interdisciplinary collaboration between teachers and students on technological projects.

Each strategy has its impact, depending on the educational context and the specific objectives to be achieved:

- If the focus is on improving teaching and learning in the classroom, the first strategy is key. The integration of educational technologies can transform the way students acquire knowledge, making it more dynamic and interactive. Teachers trained in digital tools can influence gamification and digital project-based learning to improve engagement.
- If the goal is to develop critical thinking and digital knowledge, the second strategy is invaluable. In a world where information is abundant (and not always reliable), teaching students to analyze sources, reflect on the impact of technology, and navigate the digital environment safely is essential.
- If large-scale technological innovation and development are desired, the third strategy might be more effective. Having labs equipped with AI, augmented reality, and advanced tools fosters creativity and interdisciplinary collaboration. This allows students to develop cutting-edge skills and explore technological applications in diverse areas.

Considering the difficulties involved in setting up a laboratory to implement the third strategy, we decided to create a joint strategy that linked the first two strategies. To achieve this, we sought out an existing program and adapted it to the objective conditions of the students, the professors, and the university's situation. This training lasted six months, was delivered once a week, and included study

groups.

The assessment units (DMUs) are each of the 244 students, denoted by DMU1, DMU2, ..., DMU244. The students were divided into four groups: DMG1, which includes student teachers for subjects such as Physics, Mathematics, Computer Science, and technical sciences; DMG2, which includes students specializing in biological sciences; the third group, DMG3, includes students from humanities-related pedagogical subjects such as Political Science, Philosophy, or Language; and finally, DMG4, which includes students from artistic subjects such as Music Appreciation or Visual Arts. Thus, each group consists of 61 students to be analyzed. To simplify the calculations, the results for each group are aggregated concerning all variables using Equation 6. To do this, it was determined that the dominant variable is "Digital skills after the intervention," which is denoted by v_D .

The notations for the other variables are:

v_2 : Level of digital competence before the intervention,

v_3 : Access to technology,

v_4 : Previous training,

v_5 : Productivity,

v_6 : Adoption of technological tools.

The values of the contradiction function are as follows:

$$c(v_D, v_2) = 0.5,$$

$$c(v_D, v_3) = 0.1,$$

$$c(v_D, v_4) = 0.1,$$

$$c(v_D, v_5) = 0.5,$$

$$c(v_D, v_6) = 0.3,$$

After applying the aggregation and obtaining the results for each group, the calculations obtained are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Results in the form of plithogenic neutrosophic numbers of the aggregation for each DMG and each variable.

Variable/DMGs	DMG1	DMG2	DMG3	DMG4
v_2	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)
v_3	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)
v_4	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)	(0.40, 0.70, 0.50)	(0.50, 0.40, 0.60)
v_5	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)
v_6	(0.80, 0.10, 0.30)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)
v_D	(0.95, 0.05, 0.05)	(0.80, 0.10, 0.30)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)	(0.65, 0.30, 0.45)

The plithogenic neutrosophic number values in Table 2 are obtained by aggregating the 61 values for each group using Equation 6.

Converting the elements of Table 2 into crisp values with the help of the score function in Equation 8 results in the following:

Table 3. Results in the form of crisp values of the data that appear in Table 2 after applying the score function.

Variable/DMGs	DMG1	DMG2	DMG3	DMG4
v_2	0.6333	0.5	0.3999	0.3999
v_3	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.3999
v_4	0.6333	0.5	0.3999	0.5
v_5	0.6333	0.6333	0.6333	0.6333
v_6	0.7999	0.6333	0.6333	0.6333
v_D	0.95	0.7999	0.6333	0.6333

Table 4 contains the results of applying Equation 4 to the data, which is the formula for the relationship of the data of each variable concerning the dominant attribute (Figure 1).

Table 4. Results of applying Equation 4 to the data in Table 3.

Variable/DMGs	DMG1	DMG2	DMG3	DMG4
v_2	0.79165	0.64995	0.5166	0.5166
v_3	0.545	0.52999	0.51333	0.42324
v_4	0.66497	0.52999	0.42324	0.51333
v_5	0.79165	0.7166	0.6333	0.6333
v_6	0.87495	0.7166	0.6333	0.6333
v_D	0.95	0.7999	0.6333	0.6333

Figure 1. Radar Chart of the Reescaled Performance Profiles for DMG1 to DMG4 Across Six Variables

Table 5 contains the results of the input-oriented CCR model calculations using the DEA Frontier Free Version.

Table 5. Results of the CRC Input- Oriented DEA model.

DMG name	Input-Oriented CRC efficiency	Optimal Multipliers					
		v_2	v_3	v_4	v_5	v_6	v_D
DMG1	1.00000	1.08809	0.25434	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	1.05263
DMG2	1.00000	1.53858	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	1.25016
DMG3	1.00000	1.93573	0.00000	0.00000	0.05926	0.00000	1.51977
DMG4	1.00000	1.93573	0.00000	0.00000	0.05926	0.00000	1.51977

From Table 5 and the results of the efficiency coefficients, we see that the solution to the problem is efficient because they are all equal to 1.0. That is, there is an improvement after the program was implemented.

4. Conclusion

From the systematization of the background of the problem, the central problem that we face lies in the insufficient training in basic digital skills among students at the Bolivarian University of Ecuador, which limits their ability to perform efficiently in a digital environment. If this problem were not resolved, future professionals would face difficulties adapting to the demands of the labor market, reducing their competitiveness and capacity for innovation. Therefore, we analyzed three possible strategies to apply to reverse this situation. We took two of them and transformed them into a single objective to achieve, and we also implemented a training program for students to achieve this objective. The chosen strategies were: (1) Integration of Educational Technologies in Teaching and (2) Promotion of Digital Culture and Critical Thinking. Then, we evaluated 244 students divided into four groups according to their specialty within pedagogy. We obtained improvement in all groups. One of the contributions of the article, beyond the practical result, is that we showed that plithogenic neutrosophic sets can be used in the validation of a program or project when hybridized with the DEA method, to measure the incorporation of competencies in students and teachers of higher education.

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